

EROS AND THÂNATOS IN THE VIDEO CLIP FOR *ESTRANGED* , FROM GUNS N' ROSES

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ABSTRACT

This essay explores the music, song and video for *Estranged*, by Guns N' Roses, released in 1991, on the album *Use Your Illusion II*. It is a true masterpiece of the international recording industry, and can be classified as a song that has an incomparable production, and cannot be surpassed in technical and sound terms. It's such an incredible composition that, live, you can hear the piano, guitar and double bass playing at the same level, that is, what you expect from base instruments, they are producing melody in the same timbre. This makes it no longer a rock song but a rock opera with traditional elements. The lyrics reveal Axl's feelings of fear regarding the loneliness that loomed with the end of his marriage to Erin Everlin. This feeling was due to his manic-depressive behavior, with expressions of excessive aggression and deep bouts of depression and variation in mood. The video clip represents a revelation by the vocalist about his psychic world and how he was driven to certain attitudes, especially towards death and, always, an unknown force took care of bringing him back to life. There is a detail in the performance of the song *Estranged* (when played live), which is the emotional charge that Axl imposes on it; a special type of feeling, of anguish, of melancholy, that is not noticeable in the other songs. Both the lyrics and the song were composed at a very delicate moment in Axl Rose's life, such as drug and alcohol addiction, divorce, stardom, confusion on and off stage, with the press, with his group mates, with fans and anyone who would face a good fight and, when the press realized that all that adrenaline mixed with the anger and hatred that consumed the boy, made her earn a lot of money and sell a lot of magazines, around the world she bet everything, while the young rockstar attacked her more and more, without understanding that he was playing the game she wanted so much.

Keywords: Foreign. Axl Rose. Armas e Rosas. Eros and Thanatos.

INTRODUCTION

The North American hard rock band Guns N' Roses surprised the whole world by bringing to the music scene of the 1980s a type of sound that had a peculiarity, namely its lyrics and guitar *riffs* that became iconic and emblematic thanks to a freedom to play that was unknown until then. The musical influences were explicit; But what they did was impressive,

generating an ambiguous feeling (anger and admiration, passion and hatred), both among fans and critics.

The debut album *Appetite for Destruction* (1987) proved to be a success and another one followed, *Lies* (1988), which also proved to be an electrifying, controversial production that would pave the way for the mega production released in September 1991, the double-albums *Use Your Illusion I and II*, marked by confusion, delays in production, mixing, change of members and a set of songs that would mark an era, highlighting, among them, *Estranged*, an epic of more than 9 (nine) minutes created based on the short story by Del James *Without You*, which tells the story of a young singer addicted to drugs and his girlfriend who commits suicide because of betrayal. The lyrics of the song are an outburst from the character, who is unhappy with the loss of love in such a tragic way and who finds himself forced to continue living, suffocated by guilt and who, as a result, begins to suffer from hallucinations, misunderstood, in his anguish, for his friends, who only tell him that he is under the influence of drugs.

Following the mega production of the *video* for *November Rain* (1992), the group released the *video* for *Estranged*, which would soon become epic, also, starting with the production, a work costing 9 (nine) million *dollars*, becoming the most expensive music *video* in the entire history of music, with the use of a stunt double, in a scene where Axl Rose is saved by dolphins and Slash appears on the surface of the water, performing a magnificent guitar solo.

The guitarist declared, in an interview, that this song represents the most difficult song in the band's entire repertoire for him to play live. "The most challenging guitar part is *Estranged*, which is a Guns N' Roses song. Because playing live requires a lot of concentration. It's not the typical case of turning up the volume and throwing it all in. So it took a lot of concentration to capture all the nuances of the whole song and there's a lot of arrangements and stuff going on there; so this is definitely the most challenging" (SLASH, 2023).

There is a detail in the *performance* of the song *Estranged* (when played live), which is the emotional charge that Axl imposes on it; a special type of feeling, of anguish, of melancholy, that is not noticeable in the other songs; not even in *November Rain* which, strangely, is interpreted as the most sentimental song the vocalist had ever composed. Perhaps it is this emotional charge that challenges Slash to remain faithful, since he is one of the song's composers. Both the lyrics and the song were composed at a very delicate moment in Axl Rose's life, such as drug and alcohol addiction, divorce, stardom, confusion on and off stage, with the press, with his group mates, with fans and anyone who would face a good fight and, when the press realized that all that adrenaline mixed with the anger and hatred that consumed the boy, made her earn a lot of money and sell a lot of magazines, around the world she bet everything,

while the young *rockstar* attacked her more and more, without understanding that he was playing the game she wanted so much, that is, he was being manipulated.

The song is based on the short story by Del James, an old friend of Axl Rose, *Without You*, which tells the story of a young musician, Mayne, and his girlfriend Elisabeth, who, lost in the middle of a turbulent, suicidal relationship, leaving him alone. The lyrics deal with the melancholy feelings of this young man after the incident, torn between the desire to die and the need to continue living. Eros and Thanatos in conflict.

For Mayne, the entire conflict was based on the principle that, if he left, all that [*almost*] unbearable pain would disappear; However, if you do, how could you know how to experience the *glamor* that the future envisioned for you? It was not a simple decision between doing and not doing; it was far beyond, in which only life can allow one to venture towards becoming, towards what can become, even if one does not know exactly what it is; in other words, everything in life is nothing more than an expectation.

THE STRANGED SONG

This song has one of the most introspective lyrics in the entire history of rock. It was composed in 1990, after the divorce of Axl Rose and Erin Everlin and, in the midst of turbulent psychoanalytic therapy, which he entered for five-hour sessions a day, five days a week. It presents an individual immersed in a deep existential crisis, reflecting on life and existence itself, telling himself that his loneliness is a mistake and that, the strangest thing is that no one ever says what it will be like... and , this is an anger that all humans carry against all other humans, especially against those closest to them, as if they were keeping a deep truth hidden, a secret that they refuse to reveal. It turns out that, as much as the individual lost in the midst of life and existence, they are all in the same situation of ignorance, condemned to make the same mistakes; sometimes, being induced to do so, as a form of revenge by those who felt betrayed and, the penalty imposed, however absurd it may be, is not death; it is the obligation to continue living, now without the company of the target object of your love.

At every moment, in each verse, he opposes the most complex existential question to the human being; life and death, in which the first reveals nothing to him, being a surprise at each new moment, good or bad and the second, a deprivation of all the surprise that one can have about the end of the journey undertaken. Thus, it presents to those who get lost in the process of reflection on being and existence, the emotional, pathetic conflict between Eros and Thanatos, the god of life and the god of death.

At every moment he reveals himself in conflict with the separation from his love, in which he questions why things have to be like this, confusing and, in the end, he drifts away, without a direction and dies. Perhaps because of this lack of direction, of a vision of the future for two, everything ends up meaningless, requiring explanations for what, at most, we can try to find a justification for; since neither party wants, not even any kind of explanation, because the end of a relationship represents an intimate failure and, for the woman, a crueler failure, because it shows that *she loved the wrong person!* And, this is the only thing a woman regrets.

He goes on to say that when you find all the reasons, even with all the *unstable seasons* of your life, *perhaps* you will find a new path, a new day; however, this time, without the one he believed he loved. In the poem, he uses the expression *changing seasons*, which is a pun used to hide all his anguish and melancholy heightened by the intimate discoveries he would discover throughout his therapy and even because of his stardom.

Axl was diagnosed with manic depressive disorder, that is, he presented states of euphoria and, in the next moment, he could be experiencing terrible melancholy, subjecting himself to a depressive state, in which all his anger could be a form of emotional conflict expressed in reverse. . Possibly, it was these mood attacks that led to the early end of his marriage, sinking him even further into his private depression and existential despair.

Through a hermeneutic analysis of the lyrics of *Estranged*, we understand that his relationship with Erin Everlin was fraying and getting lost in an empty space of misunderstandings and each of them was accepting this as a normal consequence of an all-too-human relationship. . She ends the poem by stating that she will never find another person who can replace her and that she never wanted the love they felt and lived to die.

The separation was a very strange chapter and event in Axl's life. Because of his constant emotional crises, he needed someone's company to contain him when he was excited and to help him stay alive when he was depressed. His relationship with his wife was one of dependence and not merely affective. I had to constantly be by his side, because he never knew when his manic episodes might appear, invading the scene and distorting his entire life with his companions.

And, where do Eros and Thanatos overlap in the song's lyrics? This is the most subtle challenge of the lyrics, which presents an enormous power of reflection and attempted understanding; but nowhere does it explicitly speak of death or rebirth; he just presents ideas of delusions in which he needs someone to say that *everything is fine* and that is not what his friends tell him, leading more to an idea of resolving everything in the most sensible way

possible: putting an end to all the pain and in all the terror. So, he says he will continue, clinging to life, alone, without the support that she had become in his life.

Individuals who suffer from manic-depressive disorder, in which their mood is quite changeable and unstable, tend to create a type of schizopathic dependence on someone, becoming an obsession, filled with jealousy and violence, which most [*otherwise* , *everyone*] considers it as a disease, when the fact is that it is a symptom arising from the operative symptomatic condition. Eros and Thanatos fighting in the same emotional space; on the one hand, moments of euphoria mark an intense production of adrenaline, full of creativity and impulses with a striking presence; however, with the condition that, in its ecstasy, if contradicted it can lead to a state of sudden fury, aggression and extreme violence; hence the need for someone with power to control over the individual, who he or she listens to and obeys. In the opposite direction of feeling, when they enter a depressive state, outbreaks of aggressiveness can occur, in which all the energy directed to the death impulse is directed, without any control, to the life impulse and, in the conflictual condition, explodes towards brutal violence. , attacking oneself; sometimes fatally.

For those who are not familiar with crisis situations, the whole thing is nothing more than an act, nervous tantrums, outbursts of humor, and such a creature should be avoided, because it is a neurasthenic and gets irritated easily; is not reliable. In a short time, there are a few friends around this individual and no one else. The social circle narrows in such a way that all that is left is nothing more than that: leftovers.

The final chorus of *Estranged* reveals this insecurity and this surreal fear of losing, not just the company of the woman he loves; but what this could represent in your life as a whole. Quite possibly, it was when he realized this situation in its deepest dimension that he decided to seek psychiatric and psychoanalytic help; It was no longer possible to live being haunted by a ghost that I couldn't defeat, simply because I didn't know him.

The song is filled with a deep melancholy, in which the guitar and piano solos contrast with the vocals, once again, a representation of the conflict between Eros and Thanatos produced in a masterful way, very much in the classic Guns n' production style. Roses that becomes epic over the years and the possibility of deep and meticulous interpretation. Slash revealed, in an interview, that this is the most difficult song to perform live, because of the piano passages, demanding more attention from him. One cannot deny the artist's own speech; but, one is free to add that the load of feelings that it contains in its sound course means that its execution is delimited within what it is.

In Paul Stenning's opinion, “*Estranged* is the glory of the album *Use Your Illusion II* [in which it represents and expresses] a surprising vision of the abysses of Axl Rose's mind. (...) It becomes apparent that this song is a description of how Axl sees himself, not only because of the problems in his youth but also because of the problems in relationships. “*Estranged* is one of many songs in which Axl shows his tendency to express himself using riddles. Instead of expressing himself clearly or writing about just one specific type of feeling, he tends to cover multiple topics and emotions in one song. One can imagine that Axl writes like a conversation, with a fast pace of thought and expressing himself carefully, exorcising his demons at the tip of his pen. Musically, the song wraps up and rolls into impetuous waves, taking almost half the song to reach the chorus, melodically worked and cultivated by the harmonious notes of Slash's guitar. Maybe it was an indication of the end of a perfect relationship for him. Axl's vocals are impeccable in the song, reaching places still unexplored by his incomparable voice” (STENNING, 2011, pp. 78-9).

It is a magnificent artistic creation, so well done that it doesn't even leave room for bold arrangements when played live. It has a double bass base to envy, which contrasts with its level of melancholy, heightened by the sound of the guitar, always dueting with the piano. This song represents the greatest musical production ever achieved and developed by a rock band, a challenge that only very prepared musicians with enough courage to risk and wait to see, not only the result, but the public's support in relation to it. , could have produced. In the history of music, it is something that was only accomplished by Axl and his companions and, if it weren't for all his rebellion, something that his friends understood, for a long time, as a *bizarre form* of leadership, this and many other highly complex songs band's musical, which became big hits, would not have been presented to the public.

THE VIDEO CLIP OF *ESTRANGED*

The song *Estranged* stood out on the album *Use Your Illusion II* for several reasons and one of them was for its production and musical quality, in which the musicians dared and built an authentic masterpiece, impossible to be reproduced live by others who were not themselves. At the end of the double album tour, Axl presents the world with a video clip of the song, in which he explores everything he has at his fingertips and to the same extent, exposes everything that explodes within him, creating a cinematic piece with an expressive psychology of such magnitude that to this day it has not been surpassed. Filming the *Estranged music video* required high-quality images of a concert, a yacht, a pool with dolphins.

The video begins with the police and SWAT invading Axl's house, accompanied by an ambulance and paramedics already rushing with a stretcher, in order to help someone who was supposedly injured at the scene. This refers to the incident involving the singer and his neighbor, in which she accused him of attacking her with a bottle of wine. The scene shows him lying in the fetal position, on top of a closet, torn between the expectation of being found and the calm of being safe, a typical feeling of a child.

In an epic scene, Axl is lying on a sofa, apparently after performing a concert and his spirit leaves his body and goes to stay under the shower, in an expression of someone looking for some kind of relief. Next, a private place appears, similar to a mansion in which everything is covered in white, including the participants. White is the color representing death; A situation that well describes Axl's feelings during the period prior to the production of the albums, a detail that is extensively explored in the music video for the song *Don't Cry*, released in 1991.

In another striking scene, he is walking along a sidewalk near a pool full of dolphins. These animals are known for the stories that they helped shipwrecked sailors find their way to the coast, in other words, saving their lives. They are symbols of joy, intelligence, protection, freedom, friendship and connection with the spiritual world. His striking presence in the video has to do with what Axl felt in his inner world; the exasperated conflict between Eros and Thanatos. The scene follows and he appears walking on the deck of a ship and suddenly throws himself into the sea, refusing a lifebuoy that is thrown to his friend Gilby. Duff appears in a boat, amid the waves trying to save him; but, once again, he refuses any kind of help from anyone; seems willing to carry out his purpose. When he surrenders to the arms of death, a dolphin appears and brings him back to the surface, where guitarist Slash appears, playing a magnificent solo, hovering over the sea waters.

The sea symbolizes the womb. Thus, when he throws himself into it, he demonstrates the desire to return to it and, when he emerges from it, he reveals rebirth. He is then rescued by his friends in a helicopter and a final scene shows Axl next to a dolphin whispering something to him and a sneaker with his name written on it arrives at the bottom of the sea, with the words: "Love your illusion!"

The video for *Estranged* is an impeccable production, with notes for the use of a stunt double in the scene in which Slash appears emerging from the water and hovers over a submarine. The original idea for the song was for the *November Rain* music video to be used in it; but, a decision by Stephanie Seymour, Axl's girlfriend at the time, meant that things were decided differently and the result was the resounding success that followed the song from *Use your Illusion I* and even with a million-dollar production, the video for *Estranged* didn't achieve

the glitz and *glamor* that its predecessor in the musical trilogy did. Even because it is a construction full of surreal symbolism and a very high enigmatic charge, conflicting in such a way that it requires very deep and complex interpretations. It is a very personal representation of Axl Rose's existence and his most intrinsic conflicts, those that exist beyond himself and that, no matter how much one tries to face them, remain present and challenging and if the tragic end did not happen it was because because of an internal conflict, too, not because of a conscious desire to move forward.

It may seem strange to say that someone's existence continues due to conflicts that are not understood and that occur in their most intrinsic worlds, far from everyone's sight; but, in Axl's case, these appear on the plane of the Ego, which can be the most conflictive of them, which makes him explode in apparently simple situations. The scene with the ship, in which he jumps into the open sea, is a revelation about how he acts when driven to something and, the most complex thing to understand, because it can turn out to be a tragic paradox, is that it was his impetuosity that gave his life a long life. his band and the musical creations, now eternal, that they produced and choreographed in a unique way, influencing through an unmistakable, incomparable and irreplaceable style.

EROS AND THÂNATOS EXPRESSED IN THE VIDEO CLIP OF *ESTRANGED*

Eros, the god of love, is a very powerful demiurge from Greek mythology, being placed in the background because of the violence he exerts on men and animals and the fear he aroused in humans and even other gods. It represents life, the continuation of life, attachment to existence, the will that leads individuals to hold on to their deepest feelings and fight for the conservation of the species. Thanatos, in turn, is the god of death, representing all detachment from the things of life and life itself.

The video *Estranged* is a reflection of the entire conflict that corrodes the intrinsic world of Axl Rose, victim of a mental illness that, in itself, already highlights abusive behaviors that go from one extreme to another, ranging from aggression towards third parties to self-harm. in different tones. Added to this was the demands of the music industry's bussiness world, excessive drugs and pressure from the press to provoke exaltation, because they knew this would lead to many newspaper covers the following morning. His friends understood how the vocalist's attitude helped them become more than excellent musicians and did little to stop him from being who he wanted to be and doing what he wanted according to his intentions, both on and off the stage.

What draws attention is that the conflict between Eros and Thanatos that took place in Axl's world was not distributed between two psychic instances, the Ego and the Id. Everything manifested and unfolded on the plane of the Ego, which is a very rare to find in the history of an individual. It was as if the desire to see the end of all that pain contrasted with the desire to see where it would all lead; the desire to be applauded and adored by their audience, a feeling that can be interpreted based on a speech Axl made during an interview, which sounds like an egoic whisper out loud, where he states that before, the group went up on stage and the audience they cursed them and spat at them; But, they had to be there. Now, they are the ones who curse and spit at them and they love them.

When Sigmund outlines his thoughts and discoveries about Psychoanalysis and its object of study, the Unconscious, he discovers that man lives, in his inner world, in a constant battle, on the one hand, an instance that wants to live according to its own dictates, whom he called Ego (*Pride* , in classical Latin) and, on the other hand, there is a primitive, violent force that fights to maintain life at any cost, the Id (a neutral pronoun in Latin, meaning *This* or *that*). He would still take some time to develop his structural concept of the Superego, which is an external agent. The Ego operates according to the pleasure principle and the Id operates according to the principle of life, of infinite existence. So, if death, the end of existence, has the power to put an end to the pain that bothers so much, that is, if it proves capable of awakening pleasure; It's worth all the sacrifice and that's where the Id will operate, not allowing this alternative to be the only one to be applied to the being, as a solution.

In the *video clip* this situation is always presented, in which even though the desire for death exists, as a way of interrupting suffering caused by a psychological illness and which proved to be impossible to overcome, the solution was to walk away and leave everything behind. walking adrift, that is, letting oneself be guided by the Ego and allowing it to satisfy itself as it sees fit; but, behold, a force of nature guides him out of his dark world and returns him to the light of existence.

From the first scene in which he appears lying in the dark and in the fetal position, which already foreshadows his desire for death, in contrast with the intrepid and quick action of the police officers who enter his house, completely immersed in darkness equipped with high-precision flashlights, opening each room in search of the individual who was out of sight but could hear them advancing through the rooms. House is a symbolism for the self and the police officers may well be representing their psychiatrist and psychotherapist who, similar to the men of the law, advanced into their world, with great caution, since they did not know what they

might find nor what surprises awaited her as she opened each room of her consciousness and unconsciousness.

Again, he finds himself in a mansion where everything is painted in white, the color of death and, in contrast to this, the garden is full of happy children, playing, as if life were eternal and emptied of problems and tensions. Once again we have the representation of his world, in which he feels dead inside and, in the same proportion, everything around him shines with joy, happiness and vigor.

In the ship scene, his step is decided and no one in this world would be able to stop him from doing what he wanted, which was to return to the mother's womb, since the sea symbolizes this condition. Gilby offers him a small uterus for rebirth, shaped like a lifebuoy, which Axl immediately refuses. Duff offers him another one, a little bigger than the first; however, tiny compared to the vastness of the ocean, which is also rejected, representing very little to guarantee a dignified existence. Thus, he surrenders himself to the passionate arms of death, which apparently welcomes him like a bride in love. Then, the great uterus itself refuses him, causing a sea creature to return him to life, when his friends rescue him *with forceps* .

In the video, Axl explores this complex relationship between his Ego and his Id, the latter to whom he always attributed the presence of someone by his side who did not allow him to go all the way with his desire for suicide. When he finds himself without his emotional support, which was his wife, Erin Everlin, who, despite all the conflicts that marked their relationship, allowed the singer to see a light at the end of the tunnel and, suddenly, there is no this brightness guiding him and then he gets lost in the midst of the conflict that only he understood and that he externalized with such vehemence and, no matter how much he tried to explain, it would be of no use, because no one would be able to understand and, worse, no one wanted to understand. it.

The video ends with the caption saying *love your illusions*, which can be interpreted as an allusion to life, since this is the first and greatest of all the illusions that one has access to, as soon as one becomes aware of their existence. Throughout the lyrics, Axl talks about illusions, the first being that everyone can deceive themselves into believing that they came into this world alone. Why does he say this? It is a portrait of his need to always be accompanied, not because he was incapable of facing life alone; but, given his special condition, there was no way he could be alone in the face of so much uncertainty that his own world and his state of being guaranteed him. Always unstable, always angry about something, always eager to see the best of everything and the best result of his works. His inability to deal with frustrations made

him an individual who depended on someone telling him that, at the right time, everything would be fine.

The exaggerations he placed on himself, in terms of demands, affected everyone around him, demanding to live with a special type of pressure that few are aware of and, the strangest thing is that it seems that his friends liked to being under such leadership that, when analyzed with due distance, appears as a puerile tyranny. A scene that reveals this, in the video, is the one in which he jumps from the deck of the ship into the high seas; His walk towards the wall is representative of a spoiled boy who has just had a big argument with his parents and is ready to take revenge on them in the cruelest way imaginable, imposing on them a guilt from which they will never be able to free themselves.

The video reveals a lot about Axl's troubled personality at that moment in his life and, quite possibly, the production of this song may have worked as a therapy, helping him to purge his demons in the only way he really could. Finally, it is the representation of a very deep personal drama that not even he was able to understand or resolve. Not because he wasn't capable of it; is that the conflict was at a different level of action, there was no dialogue between the Ego and the Id and, to everyone's greatest surprise, the Superego, which was the one who should act to keep it under control, did so in the opposite direction, always encouraging increasingly aggressive and suicidal behavior.

CONCLUSION

Estranged represents much more than incredible, well-composed music, as well as having an irreparable production. It became, over time, a true epic, yielding studies on its surrealist and introspective lyrics and musical *performance*, in addition to the famous *video clip*, which is also historic, for countless reasons. The song was played live, for the first time, on January 20, 1991, at the *Roki in Rio II event*, months before the official release of the albums *Illusion I* and *II*, which would take place in September of the same year.

Estranged was played live very frequently during the *Use Your Illusion Tour*, which lasted between 1991 and 1993. Inexplicably, after the release of the *video* it fell into oblivion for the band and, only in December 2008, Axl spoke of his desire to bring it back. back to *the setlist* of the band. The song was played live by the band again after 18 years at the *Rock in Rio 2011 edition*, on October 3, 2011, at the closing of the festival, and after that it was played at all shows on the tour of America, in 2011. The song was played at every show on Guns' *Not in This Lifetime tour*, which ran from April 1, 2016, to November 2, 2019.

As presented and discussed throughout this essay, this is a song with a very personal content for Axl and, when the album tour ended, despite them all being very worn out from time on the road, the vocalist had, in some way, He found his emotional balance when it came to his relationship with Erin Everly, and there was no longer any point in exploring what had happened to find his state of egoic well-being. In this field I had already gone from egodystonic to egosyntonic. When he thinks about playing it live again, he is testing his feelings in relation to what could cause it, which could even be an imbalance and he needed to know how to behave, if this happened. The most intriguing and conflicting thing was resisting bringing her to light again for another three years, fighting the desire to do so and the fear of the consequences, which only proves that old emotional wounds would be opened.

Possibly, it is this emotional cathexis that makes Slash the most difficult song to play live on guitar. Axl's emotional involvement with the song demands more attention from the musicians regarding possible errors and, at the same time, deprives them of their freedom to dare to create creative arrangements. Everyone knows that, in harmonic and orchestral terms, it is an unparalleled, insurmountable, incomparable, irreplaceable creation.

Axl faced many problems in his life and most of them cannot be taken as his sole fault, given his diagnosis of personality disorder (manic-depressive) and which, paradoxically, robbed him of his life and existence as much as he did. bestowed in terms of glory, fame and success. The song *Estranged* showed his human side; the song revealed his most genius and creative side in the phonography that, alongside a musician who knows how to capture the whispers of a bold spirit like no other, built the most complex and profound song in the history of rock. The *Estranged video clip* reveals the conflict that exists in the vocalist's psychic world and even much more than that, that his Ego was the one who determined all things and the direction in which they should follow, even though his unconscious was not so powerful to the point of dominate him, lacking someone with enough power to stop him in his attacks of fury and to elevate him intrinsically, in moments of anguish and melancholy. This someone should be chosen by himself, revealing, once again, that we are faced with an individual who is unaware of any type of law other than his own or any dictate that is in conflict with his own desire.

The *Estranged video* could well represent the most aesthetic way that Axl found to shed light on his troubled psychic world, revealing much more about his posture and way of being in the world. Mysteriously, it is released at the end of a long and exhausting *tour* , after which everything fell apart for what was left of the band, as its main composer had left for reasons that are still unclear. What is clear is that, thanks to the genius of Axl and his friends, the world

of music experienced one of the greatest phonographic and audiovisual productions in history; complex, electrifying, creative, innovative and full of strong emotions and very revealing about the Self of an icon in conflict with himself.

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